

FABRICATION OF NANOCARRIERS EMULSOMAL GEL COMPRISING LOPINAVIR

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Abstract: Emulsomes are a type of lipid-based nanoparticle that consists of a solid lipid core surrounded by a phospholipid bilayer and have shown promise as drug delivery systems for a variety of applications. The major advantageous aspect of employing lipid-based carriers is their ability to enhance the solubility and bioavailability of poorly water-soluble drugs, mandatorily in case of intranasal drug delivery. These structures have portrayed significant ability to encapsulate drug with poor water solubility and low oral bioavailability, further leading to a completely enhanced drug delivery systems for achieving stability and controlled release of drug. The selection of lipid components and their physiochemical properties can be tailored to optimize drug solubility, blood brain barrier permeability, and enhanced targeting

Keywords: Transdermal drug delivery, Nano drug delivery, Nano carriers, Emulsomal gel, lopinavir

Introduction: Transdermal drug delivery is the non-invasive delivery of medications from the surface of skin-the largest and most accessible organ of human body- through its layers, to the circulatory system. TDDS offers many advantages over conventional injection and oral methods [1]. Transdermal delivery not only provides controlled, constant administration of the drug, but also allows continuous Input of drugs with short biological half-lives and eliminates pulsed entry into systemic circulation, which often

causes undesirable side effects the common ingredients which are used for the preparation of TDDS. Several important advantages of transdermal drug delivery are limitation of hepatic first-pass metabolism, enhancement of therapeutic efficiency, and maintenance of steady plasma level of the drug [2]. Nanostructured lipid carriers (NLCs) are novel pharmaceutical formulations which are composed of physiological and biocompatible lipids, surfactants and co-surfactants. Over time, as a second-generation lipid nanocarrier NLC has emerged as an alternative to first generation nanoparticles [3]. Emulsomes, which are nanoparticles made of lipid, are frequently utilized as drug delivery mechanisms. Their structure can be compared to a cross between liposomes and solid lipid nanoparticles because they are made up of an oil phase enclosed by a phospholipid bilayer. A head-to-tail arrangement of two layers of phospholipids, with their hydrophilic heads facing outward and their hydrophobic tails facing inside, forms the phospholipid bilayer in emulsomes. This bilayer gives the emulsomes a stable structure and works to keep the encapsulated oil phase from deteriorating [4]. Emulsomes offer a sustained and regulated release of the medication. Emulsomes offer a longer drug release than liposomes, up to 24 h, while liposomes exhibit only a release for up to 6 h. Emulsomes are nanoscale in size when compared to various vesicular delivery systems including niosomes, pharmacosomes, and ethosomes [5]. Emulsomes can contain high concentrations of hydro-phobic medications in their cores while encapsulating therapeutics that are water soluble that is found in the aqueous compartments of the outer phospholipid layers. Emulsomes improve the bioavailability and solubility of lipophilic medicines, and their structure allows for sustained or regulated drug release [6].

Material and Methods:

Preparation of nanocarriers emulsomal gel formulation: The emulsomal gel formulation was prepared with nanocarriers emulsomes and gel base (GB4) to get LEMs1 – LEMs6 and evaluated as parameters discussed earlier. The quantities of gel ingredients showed in **Table 1**. The various polymers such as hydroxypropylmethylcellulose (HPMC, 2gm), were used with Propylene glycol (10ml) dissolved in 10 ml of denaturated alcohol (10ml) in beaker. The dissolved mucilaginous materials were stirred at high-speed using mechanical stirrer. Now, triethanolamine (1.5 ml) was added slowly to the beaker containing above mixture liquid dispersion while stirring. The crushed menthol

(100 mg) was incorporated slowly in above dispersion after smooth dispersion is obtained. The prepared emulsomal gel was finally transferred in aluminum collapsible tube and labelled.

Table 1: Formulae of nanocarriers emulsomal gel

Formulation Code	Lipid content (X ₁)			Amount of surfactant (X ₂) (%)		Addition of sonication time (X ₃) (Min.)
	Spermaceti (SM) (mg) X _a	Glycerol monostearate (GMS) (mg) X _b	Triglycerides (Trimyristin) (TM) (mg) X _c	Tween 20	Tween 80	
LEM _s 1	50	150	100	5	0	5
LEM _s 2	50	150	100	10	0	5
LEM _s 3	50	150	100	15	0	5
LEM _s 4	50	150	100	0	5	5
LEM _s 5	50	150	100	0	10	5
LEM _s 6	50	150	100	0	15	5

Evaluation of nanocarriers emulsomal gel formulation:

Physical appearance: The physical appearance of prepared nanocarriers emulsomal gel was visually checked as parameters i.e. colour, appearance and feel on application.

pH determination: The pH of nanocarriers emulsomal gel were determined by using the digital pH meter. 1 gram of gel was dissolved in 100 ml distilled water and stored for two hours. pH electrodes were completely dipped into the formulations and pH was noted. The measurement of pH of each formulation was done in triplicate manner and average values were calculated.

Extrudability determination: The nanocarriers emulsomal gel was filled into collapsible metal tubes. The tubes were pressed with same pressure by using fingers and the extrudability of the formulations was checked. The extrudability of the formulation

was determined in terms of weight in grams required to extrude a 0.5 cm ribbon of gel in 10 seconds.

Viscosity determination: The viscosity of the prepared nanocarriers emulsomal gel was measured by Brook field viscometer. The sufficient quantity of gel base was filled in wide mouth jar separately and it should sufficiently allow dipping the spindle. The RPM of the spindle was adjusted to 2.5 RPM. The viscosities of the formulations were recorded.

Spreadability: Spreadability means the extent of area to which nanocarriers emulsomal gel readily spreads on application to skin or affected part of skin. The therapeutic potency of a formulation also depends upon its spreading value. Spreadability of formulation is expressed in terms of time in seconds taken by two slides to slip off from gel base, which is placed in between the slides under the direction of certain load.

Lesser the time taken for the separation of two slides, better the spreadability. It is calculated by using the formula

$$S = M * L / T$$

where, M = Weight tied to upper slide; L = Length of glass slide; T = Time taken to separate the slides

Homogeneity: The nanocarriers emulsomal gel has been set in the container; all prepared gels were tested for homogeneity by visual inspection. They were tested for their appearance and presence of any lumps, flocculates or aggregates.

Grittiness: The nanocarriers emulsomal gel was evaluated microscopically for the presence of any appreciable particulate matter under light microscope. The preparation should free from particles and the grittiness of any topical preparation can check.

Determination of Entrapment Efficiency: The entrapment efficiency was determined after separation of the untrapped drug by the use of minicolumn centrifugation method. Sephadex G-50 (1.2gm) was swelled in 20 ml of 0.9% NaCl solution for 5 hours at room temperature with occasional shaking. The gel was formed and it was stored at 4°C. To prepare the minicolumn, the hydrated gel was filled up to top in the barrel of 1mL disposable syringe, plugged with whatman filter pad. Then barrel placed in the centrifuge and centrifuged at 2000 rpm for 3 min to remove saline solution. Eluted volume was

removed from the centrifuged tubes and exactly 0.2mL of nanocarriers emulsomal gel suspension (undiluted) was applied drop wise on the gel bed in the center. Columns were again centrifuged at 2000 rpm for 3 min to expel and remove void volume containing emulsomes to the centrifuge tubes. Elute was remove and 0.25 mL of saline was applied to each column and centrifuge as previously. The amount of drug entrapped in the vesicle was then determined by disrupting the vesicle using 1 ml of 0.1%v/v triton-X 100, filtering it and the drug content was determined using UV-Vis spectroscopy at 234 nm. The percentage efficiency was determined by following equation:

$$\text{Percentage drug entrapment efficiency} = \frac{\text{Amount of entrapped}}{\text{Total amount of drug}} \times 100$$

in-vitro diffusion studies: Before experiment, the cellophane membrane was washed in the running water and then soaked in distilled water for 24 h to remove glycerine present on membrane. The release of herbal gel was studied by dialysis method in pH 7.4 artificial skin pH. 2 ml samples were instilled in the dialysis bag which was screwed with two clamps at each end. The dialysis bag was dipped into the receptor compartment containing 35 ml of dissolution medium and stirred continuously at 100 rpm. The donor compartment was kept in contact with a receptor compartment and the temperature was maintained at $37 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$. The receptor compartment was closed to prevent evaporation of the dissolution medium. The solution on the receptor side was stirred by externally driven teflon coated magnetic bars. At predetermined time intervals, 5 ml of solution from the receptor compartment was pipette out and immediately replaced with fresh 5 ml phosphate buffer. Samples were withdrawn at regular time intervals, and the same volume was replaced with fresh dissolution medium. The amount of drug entrapped in the vesicle was then determined by disrupting the vesicle using 1 ml of 0.1%v/v triton-X 100, filtering it and the drug content was determined using UV-Vis spectroscopy at 234 nm. Calculation of percentage drug release was done using the formula:

$$\% \text{ drug release} = \frac{(\text{Conc. of drug (in mg)} \times \text{Volume of receptor compartment}) \times 100}{\text{Label claim (amount of drug in donor compartment)}}$$

Results and discussion:

Optimization of nanocarriers emulsomes for types of surfactants, concentration of surfactant and Sonication time

The physical evaluation as the colour of prepared nanocarriers emulsomal gels was light yellow colour to Pale yellow colour in colour and appearance of nanocarriers emulsomal gel was transparent and translucent in nature and smooth on application at skin. The individual properties such as consistency of formulations were good and texture of prepared emulsomal gel was found to be smooth.

Table 2: Characterization of nanocarriers emulsomes

Formulation Code	Particle size (nm)	Zeta potential (mV)	PDI	Drug Entrapment (%)
LEMGs1	151.11±1.01	-21.11±0.11	0.231±0.54	81.25±0.2
LEMGs2	152.01±1.11	-21.01±0.13	0.230±0.41	83.05±0.5
LEMGs3	153.81±1.11	-21.13±0.13	0.229±0.79	85.12±0.2
LEMGs4	141.11±1.12	-21.07±0.41	0.229±0.61	82.75±0.5
LEMGs5	150.14±1.11	-20.98±0.21	0.228±0.78	84.15±0.7
LEMGs6	148.07±1.01	-20.12±1.01	0.229±0.55	88.32±0.5

The pH value of the prepared gel formulation was observed at room temperature and valued range at 7.03 to 8.21. The literature informed that from epidermis to dermis, pH of the skin increases and attained the neutral value. The results of gel formulation having pH range 7.0 to 7.6 are desirable to skin pH, since they do not interfere with the physiology of skin. The prepared nanocarriers emulsomal gel formulations were evaluated for good extrudibility due to having good viscous property. These nanocarriers emulsomal gels stored to accelerated stability testing. All prepared nanocarriers emulsomal gels were stored at 4⁰ C, 25⁰ C and 45⁰ C in refrigeration, room temperature and stability chamber for a period of 30 days to study effect of temperature and at different humidity condition. The physical parameters were evaluated during study period. The result of the study

indicates that the preparation is physically stable at all temperatures during storage period. The result concluded that **LEMGs5** was best formulation under all observations (**Table 2-3**).

Table 3: Characterization of nanocarriers emulsomal gel

Parameters	Formulations					
	LEMGs1	LEMGs2	LEMGs3	LEMGs4	LEMGs5	LEMGs6
Colours	Pale yellow colour					
Appearance	Translucent	Translucent	Translucent	Translucent	Transparent	Transparent
Odour	Pleasant odour	Pleasant odour	Pleasant odour	Pleasant odour	Define odour	Define odour
Feel of application	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth
Spreadability (g.cm/sec)	12.5	8.4	8.9	13.2	8.9	10.1
Consistency	Good	Poor	Poor	Poor	Fairly good	Excellent uniform
pH	6.43	6.18	6.88	6.22	7.98	7.54
Viscosity (cps)	0.91	0.94	0.91	0.88	0.86	1.06
Extrudibility	Good	Poor	Poor	Good	Good	Excellent
Stability	Stable	Stable	Stable	Stable	Stable	Stable
Drug content (%)	99.82	99.41	99.64	99.91	99.71	99.81

Conclusion: One of the most effective antiviral drugs for viral infections is lopinavir (LPV). One new kind of lipoidal vesicular system is the nanocarrier emulsome, which consists of a phospholipid bilayer encasing an internal solid fat core. For medications that are not very soluble in water, there is a new nanocarrier technique called nanocarrier emulsome. It has properties of both emulsions and liposomes. With the ability to increase anti-cancer effectiveness while decreasing skin irritation, nanocarrier emulsomes provide a promising method for topical drug administration. This is because to their high retention flux and high skin retention of medication. The suggested study set out to create a carrier technology that might carry antiviral medication topically without causing any side effects or toxicity. The emulsomal gel was made and tested using a number of

criteria. The created emulsomal gels passed the physical examination with flying colors: a pale-yellow hue, complete transparency, and a silky-smooth texture. There is no interference with skin physiology by the formulation's pH. The results showed that out of all the observations, LEMGs5 was the best formulation. The formulations' in-vitro drug release kinetics and perfusion profiles followed the Fickian diffusion and supercase II transport mechanisms, with values of $n > 0.5$.

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